

Development and Validation of a Titrimetric Method for Quantitative Determination of Free Organic Acids in Green Tea Leaves

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ABSTRACT

Introduction. Organic acids are a groups of compounds exhibiting a wide range of biological activities and some of them are included in different medicines. The search for new plant sources rich in organic acids, as well as the development of methods for their quantitative determination in plant raw materials is an interesting topic of research.

The aim of study was to develop and validate a titrimetric method with potentiometric detection of the end-point for quantitative determination of free organic acids in green tea leaves.

Research methods. A titrimetric method for the quantitative determination of free organic acids was developed and validated as per ICH guidelines.

Results and discussions. The linear regression data for the calibration curve showed a good linear relationship over the concentration range 0.72 % to 3.75%. Linear regression was found to be $y = 0.2834x + 0.0164$ ($r = 0.9992$). The percentage recovery was found to be in the range from 98.08 to 101.92 % with a %RSD value of 1.73 %. The %RSD of repeatability and intermediate precision were to be 1.76 and 1.59 %, respectively. The %RSD of stability was found to be 1.24 %. The method was confirmed to be accurate and precise having %RSD values of less than 2% in all studies. The amount of total free organic acids in green tea leaves was quantified to be 1.82 %.

Conclusions. The titrimetric method of quantitative determination of free organic acids in green tea leaves was developed and validated according to the following parameters: specificity, linearity, accuracy, repeatability, intermediate precision, stability. The proposed titrimetric method can be used for routine analysis for determination free organic acids in green tea leaves and quality control purpose as the developed method is simple, rapid, accurate and sufficiently precise.

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Introduction

Organic acids are aliphatic or aromatic compounds, which are characterized by the presence of one or more carboxyl groups¹. They are important in biological processes, since they are involved in various fundamental pathways in plant and animal metabolism and catabolism as intermediate or final products, playing a key role in the citric acid cycle or Krebs cycle².

Organic acids possess antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial and immunomodulatory activity. In addition, they create favorable conditions for the vital activity of beneficial intestinal microorganisms³⁻⁶.

Green tea has a global popularity and includes several varieties of tea. The main compounds of chemical composition of green tea are phenolic acids, polyphenolic compounds, caffeine as well as amino acids, organic acids and fats⁷. Literature survey shows that green tea contains oxalic acid (0.3 – 1.5%), quinic acid (0.07 – 1%), citric acid (0.20%), succinic acid (0.25%) and malic acid (0.25%). Among the organic acids detected in tea, oxalic acid is of importance, as it might contribute to kidney stone formation⁸. However, in human studies, it has been shown that oxalic acid from tea did not dramatically elevate urine oxalic acid levels⁹. Other studies recognized a protection against urinary stones by tea due to its antioxidant properties¹⁰.

A search of recent publications in Pubmed and ScienceDirect shows that there is no titrimetric method for quantitative determination of free organic acids in green tea leaves. In the contemporary literature, organic acids are determined by ion chromatography, capillary electrophoresis, gas chromatography and chromatography mass-spectrometry¹¹⁻¹⁶. Chromatographic methods of analysis have been proposed for quantification of organic acids, as well. There is no doubt that chromatographic methods are precise and accurate, but they require qualified analysts, and relatively expensive instrumentation.

Therefore, a titrimetric method was chosen for the determination of organic acids in green tea leaves and the aim of the current study was to develop and validate such a method.

Materials and methods

The object of the study was green tea leaves (*Camellia sinensis L.*), which was collected in Anhui province, China. A Hanna 2550 pH meter with HI 1131P potentiometric electrode was used. All titrations were carried out manually. Free organic acids were titrated using a micro burette with Class A accuracy.

Citric acid was purchased from Sigma Aldrich ($\geq 98\%$), NaOH was of analytical grade. In order to prepare NaOH solution with the concentration of 0.05 M, 1.0 g of NaOH was dissolved in distilled water. The solution was diluted to 250 mL with the same water and standardized.

Preparation of total free organic acids from green tea

Dried leaves of green tea were grinded in the size 1-2 mm. The extraction of free organic acids was carried out by distilled water on water bath in a flask with a ground glass joint, which was equipped by a condenser and extracted for different time (from 30 to 120 min) at different temperature (from 20 ° to 100 °C), while the ratio of material to liquid ranged from 1:20 to 1:90 and extraction cycles ranged from 1 to 4.

Procedure for the quantitative determination of free organic acids

The content of free organic acids in the solution was calculated from the value of the equivalent volume of titrant. The equivalent volume of the titrant was determined by a constructed differential curve in the coordinates $\Delta E/\Delta V - V$. The equivalence point was fixed at the maximum on the constructed differential curve. The perpendicular line was dropped to the horizontal axis (Volume of the titrant) through the maximum and the volume of the titrant which was spent on titration was found (**Fig 1.**).

A blank experiment was also performed. According to it, the blank volume of 0.05 M sodium hydroxide was 0.03 mL.

The content of free organic acids (X, %) in terms of citric acid in completely dry raw materials was calculated by the following formula:

Figure 1. Potentiometric titration curve of the determination of total free organic acids in green tea leaves

$$X = \frac{(V_{eq} - V_x) \cdot 0.0032 \cdot 100 \cdot 100 \cdot 100 \cdot K}{m \cdot 5 \cdot (100 - W)}$$

where, 0.0032 – the amount of citric acid, which is equivalent to 1 mL of sodium hydroxide solution (0.05 mol/L), g; V_{eq} is the volume of sodium hydroxide solution (0.05 mol/L), which was used for titration, mL; V_x – the volume of sodium hydroxide solution (0.05 mol/L), which was spent for titration in a blank experiment, mL; m – the mass of the raw materials used, g; K is correction coefficient for 0.05 mol/L sodium hydroxide solution; W – the loss in mass upon drying of the raw materials, %.

Optimization of organic acids extraction

In order to find the best conditions for the extraction of organic acids, the effects of the following influencing factors on extraction were evaluated: ratio of material to liquid, temperature, extraction cycles and duration of extraction. Factors are displayed in **Table 1**.

Validation

Validation of the titrimetric method for the quantitative determination of the amount of free organic acids in green tea leaves by potentiometric titration was performed according to the International Conference

on Harmonization (ICH) guidelines¹⁸. The titrimetric method proposed was validated on the following parameters: specificity, accuracy, linearity, repeatability, intermediate precision, stability.

The specificity of the method was studied by potentiometric titration of the solvent.

The accuracy was verified by the method of additives in a triplicate analysis of three levels of concentration of free organic acids corresponding to 40, 60, 80 % of the working concentrations of free organic acids. The standard solution of citric acid was prepared as follows: 0.072 g (accurate weight) of citric acid was placed in a 200.0 mL volumetric flask, and the solution was diluted to the volume with distilled water. Then, an aliquot of the resulting standard solution of 2.00, 3.00, 4.00 mL was taken and placed in a 100 mL flask. After that 5.00 mL of the extract obtained from green tea leaves was added to the 100 mL flask, then 45.0 mL of distilled water was added, and the solution was titrated. The evaluation criterion in determining the accuracy was the value of the relative standard deviation (RSD), which according to the requirements should be not more than 2 %, and the percentage of recovery should be from 95 to 105 %.

The linearity of the method was studied at 9 concentration levels (40, 60, 80, 100, 120, 140, 160, 180, 200%) of the theoretical content of the total amount of free organic acids (calculated with reference to citric

Table 1: The influence of various factors on the completeness of the extraction of free organic acids from green tea leaves				
Ration of material to liquid	Temperature, °C	Extraction cycles	Duration of extraction, min	The total content of free organic acids*, %±CI
ration of material to liquid				
1:20	100	1	30	1.48±0.07
1:30				1.32±0.11
1:50				1.18±0.06
1:90				1.05±0.10
temperature				
1:20	20	1	30	1.19±0.06
	40			1.24±0.13
	60			1.30±0.07
	80			1.40±0.22
	100			1.45±0.15
extraction cycles				
1:20	100	1	30	1.50±0.11
		2		0.32±0.04
		3		0.10±0.01
		4		0.03±0.01
duration of extraction				
1:20	100	2	30	1.57±0.06
			60	1.64±0.06
			90	1.75±0.10
			120	1.81±0.04

* Average of five measurements, CI - confidence interval

Figure 2: Calibration curve of the titrant volume against concentration of free organic acids

acid, %) in green tea leaves. In order to evaluate linearity of the method, different masses of raw material were taken 0.8; 1.2; 1.6; 1.8; 2.0; 2.4; 3.2; 3.6; 4.0 g (exact mass). After that each mass was extracted by the developed procedure. The quantitative content of the total amount of free organic acids in green tea leaves in the obtained solutions was then quantified by titrimetric method of titration. The linear regression was calculated by the method of least squares to obtain the regression equation and determine the correlation coefficient (r). According to the requirements of ICH, the value of the correlation coefficient when studying the linearity of the analytical method for determining the quantitative content of the active substance should be ≥ 0.999 .

The repeatability of the method was checked by preparing an extract of green tea leaves from 6 portions of the raw material within a short period of time using the same set of reagents and with the participation of the same analyst. The intermediate precision was determined as described above in the same laboratory, but in different days. The acceptance criterion is expressed by the value of the %RSD, which should not exceed 2 %.

The stability of the potentiometric procedure was carried out, too. The acceptance criterion is expressed by the value of the relative standard deviation, which should not exceed 2 %.

Table 2: The results of the titration to prove the specificity of the developed method

V_{titrant} , mL	Content of free organic acids, %	Statistical analysis*
Blank experiment (titration of distilled water)		
0.03	0.05	$0.045 \pm 0.02\%$ $s_x = 0.0014$
0.02	0.035	
0.03	0.05	
Results of titration of extract of green tea leaves		
0.57	1.00	$1.00 \pm 0.02\%$ $s_x = 0.0033$
0.56	0.99	
0.57	1.00	

*Average of three measurements, $P = 95\%$

The statistical processing of experimental data obtained was performed in accordance with the monograph «Statistical analysis of the results of a chemical experiment» of the State Pharmacopeia of Ukraine.

Table 3: Recovery studies by standard additions technique

Amount present, g	Amount added of citric acid, g	Amount taken of organic acids, g	Amount recovered, g	Recovery, %	RSD, %
0.036	0.015	0.052	0.051	98.08	1.73
			0.053	101.92	
			0.052	100.00	
0.036	0.022	0.058	0.059	101.72	
			0.058	100.00	
			0.057	98.28	
0.036	0.029	0.065	0.065	100.00	
			0.066	101.54	
			0.064	98.46	

Results and discussions

It was found that the most complete extraction of organic acids from green tea leaves can be achieved by 2 cycles of extraction at 100 °C with the ratio of material to liquid – 1:20 within 120 min. The results of study are represented in **Table 1**.

According to the obtained results, a procedure for the quantitative determination of free organic acids in green tea was developed: 2.0 g (exact mass) of the grinded raw material (2.0 mm) was placed in a 100 mL flask with ground glass joints, poured with 40 mL of distilled water; then the flask was equipped with a condenser and kept for 120 min in boiling water bath at 100 °C. Extraction was repeated once more. After cooling, the solutions were quantitatively transferred into a 100 mL volumetric flask and make up to the mark by distilled water (solution A).

5.00 mL of the solution A was placed in a 100 mL flask and 45.0 mL of distilled water was added. After adding each portion of sodium hydroxide, the solution was mixed thoroughly and the electrode potential was recorded.

The method was validated according to the ICH

Table 4: Repeatability results for free organic acids in green tea leaves

Number of samples	Content of free organic acids, %
1	1.86
2	1.81
3	1.83
4	1.85
5	1.77
6	1.83
Mean, %	1.83
SD	0.0321
Confidence interval (P=95%), %	0.03
RSD, %	1.76

Table 5: Intermediate precision results for free organic acids in green tea leaves

Number of samples	Content of free organic acids, %	
	The first day	The second day
1	1.83	1.85
2	1.81	1.86
3	1.86	1.80
4	1.84	1.83
5	1.82	1.87
6	1.78	1.79
Mean, %	1.82	1.83
SD	0.0269	0.0311
Confidence interval (P=95%), %	0.02	0.02
Mean, %	1.48	1.69

guideline for the Validation of analytical procedures Q2((Q1A (R2) 2003, Q2A 1994, Q2B 1996). The extracts of green tea were prepared as per the procedure given above.

When studying the specificity of the method, it was shown that the solvent used in the samples preparation and the probable impurities did not affect the result of the quantification of the amount of free organic acids in green tea leaves (**Table 2**).

Linearity was proven in the concentration range from 0.72 % to 3.75%. The regression equation of the curve had the following form: $y = 0.2834x + 0.0164$. The value of the correlation coefficient (r) was equal to 0.9991 (**Fig. 2**).

The accuracy of the method was assessed using the percentage of recovery and the relative standard deviation. The percentage of recovery was found to be in the range from 98.08 to 101.92 %, the value of the %RSD when assessing the correctness of the method was 1.73 % and did not exceed 2 % (**Table 3**).

The precision of the method was confirmed by re-

Table 6: Stability result for free organic acids in green tea leaves

t, min	Content of free organic acids, %
0	1.85
15	1.82
30	1.81
45	1.80
60	1.79
Mean, %	1.81
SD	0.0225
Confidence interval (P=95%), %	0.02
RSD, %	1.24

peatability and intermediate precision. The values of %RSD for repeatability and intermediate precision were 1.76 and 1.59 %, respectively. The %RSD values were less than 2 % proving that the method is precise (**Tables 4,5**).

The stability of the method was determined for 60 min. It was found that the RSD value was 1.24 %. The %RSD value was less than 2 %, showing that analytical solution is stable during 60 min and there is no significant change in the result (**Table 6**).

Conclusions

The titrimetric method for quantitative determination of free organic acids in green tea leaves was developed and validated according by the following parameters: specificity, linearity, accuracy, repeatability, intermediate precision and stability. The proposed titrimetric method can be used for routine analysis for determination free organic acids in green tea leaves and quality control purpose as the developed method is simple, rapid, accurate and sufficiently precise. □

Conflict of Interests: None declared.

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